

GOOD GOVERNANCE AND ITS IMPACT ON ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT: A SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW

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Disclosure statement:

Authors are not aware of any findings that might be perceived as affecting the objectivity of this study.

Conflict of interest:

The authors report no conflict interest

Cite this article:

Khouya, M., Benabdelhadi, A. (2020). GOOD GOVERNANCE AND ITS IMPACT ON ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT: A SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW. *International Journal of Accounting, Finance, Auditing, Management and Economics*, 1(1), 47-67.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3936217

Published online: 10 July 2020

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Abstract

Good governance is a polymorphous concept that stems from economic and political science. It is used both in the context of the management of public action and in a strategic perspective of economic development. In this article, we are first interested in deconstructing the various contributions to define and reaffirm the role of "good governance" in development strategies. What is "good governance"? How does it have an impact on a country's economy?

This paper addresses the issue of causality between good governance and economic development, by examining the inter-connections between economic development and governance indicators to increase transparency and efficiency. The purpose of this article is to organize a systematic literature review in a scientific manner from data collection, through data selection, reading and finally data analysis.

The impact of good Governance in economic development differs in political system structure, governance current characteristics and contextual factors. Although outcome factors are influenced by contextual determinants, the governance characteristics are of great importance.

Keywords: Good Governance, Economic Development, Public Governance, Governance Indicators, Growth.

JEL Classification: H00, F63

Paper type: Theoretical Research

1. Introduction

Nowadays, the importance of the economic and social role of the Administration, in a context of limited overall means and a continuously changing environment, calls for an appreciable analysis as accurate as possible of the effects and impacts of the actions carried out by the public authorities in the area of Good Governance on the economic development of the country. Good governance implies a particular conception of the disclosure of the collective interests of the stakeholders, the areas of public action and their coordination, with the aim of carrying out effective and efficient public policies.

What is good governance? Public governance? What is its impact on the economy? The academic literature on governance, which is increasing each year exponentially, provides a plethora of definitions and connections. Indeed, the purpose of this paper is to introduce, deconstruct, clarify and crossbreed the different ideas of the authors who have acquired knowledge in this area.

Like most concepts in social, economic and political sciences, governance is not a new term. In fact, the term governance was first used in France in the fourteenth century where it meant “seat of government” The term became much more popular when the World Bank ‘reinvented’ governance in a World Bank Report of 1989. The use of the term governance by the World Bank signaled a new approach to development that was based on the belief that economic prosperity is not possible without a minimum level of rule-of-law and democracy. At the same time, use of the seemingly apolitical term “governance” was valuable in preventing criticism that the World Bank was trying to interfere in the political decisions made by debtor countries (Bovaird & Loeffler, 2004).

The concept of governance has been discussed in political science and public administration research for decades. Governance-broadly defined as the framework of rules, institutions, and practices by which authority is exercised- is a key foundation of a well-functioning market economy and a major ingredient to growth and equitable development (Al-Marhubi, 2004).

Indeed, governance can be addressed analytically by describing institutions as ‘the patterns that emerge from the governing activities of social, political and administrative actors’ but also by emphasizing processes meant for guiding, steering, controlling or managing sectors or facets of societies (Kooiman, 2003).

The paper cannot and does not pretend to provide answers to all the questions, but instead opens the way for discussion and clarification, by presenting a systemic literature review, and exploring some of the many ways in which governance can impact the economy in general, and economic development in particular.

2. Research Methodology

The key to doing research is through research. That is to mean that writing a scientific article only starts with a scientific collection of references, which allows a scientific filtering based on what is essential to read. As mentioned in the introduction, the purpose is to deconstruct the subject of the research study. So, a part of this present paper aims to follow a scientific way to choose the references, and to conduct a literature review that is firstly exploratory, and secondly comprehensive in-depth literature review.

By the way, Systematic Literature Reviews are rapidly growing in importance in the social sciences to aggregate findings across multiple empirical studies, a method which extensively has been used in medical disciplines (Bilotta et al., 2014; Kampen and Tama´s, 2013; Moore et al., 2014). The first step in building up a literature review is to collect references, i.e. the various works that have been conducted to identify the research subject. The effective method

is to search directly in scientific databases controlled, by keywords, which is generally the core concept of the work "Governance".

Because of the surprisingly relative few numbers of references appearing in the searches, I needed to make a modification. So I've added other terms to the main keyword, namely "good governance", "public governance", "governance AND economic development". To filter my references in function of my research requirements, and to appropriate it to the research issue.

This effective process has excluded for example research that has been made on corporate governance, or environmental governance and has included only "public governance" documents.

2.1 Exploratory systematic literature review

The exploratory systemic literature review is used to explore all of the references discovered, in order to select the most pertinent references to read.

To do this, I have put all the references in my electronic library. I have chosen Zotero as my reference management software, which allowed me to collect all the documents in an organized way.

In addition, I opted for Zotero because it is free, and open source, and I did a doctoral course on its handling and manipulation. It enables to manage, easily and simply, bibliographic data and research documents.

In this sense, I have filled the metadata for each scientific paper, so I have mentioned the author, the year, the name of the database in which I founded the document, the name of the journal concerning the articles. And the abstract of each one.

Table 1 : References by type

Type	Number of documents
Conference paper	5
Thesis	8
Book	26
Book chapter	27
Journal article	226
Total	292

Source: *Author's processing.*

My collected references include (Tab.1) a few theses to understand the structure of writing a scientific manuscript, a few books that treat governance in a detailed way, a few chapters including the contribution of authors among others who collaborate in a shared book. And a wide range of scientific articles (just five from conferences) the rest are journal articles, which is particularly the basis for this paper.

Afterwards, I downloaded my entire library and transferred it to the Nvivo¹ software to proceed with the textual analysis, at the first stage this analysis only concerns the abstracts of each single document.

2.1.1 Word cloud

After transferring all the bibliographical documents into the Nvivo software, I proceeded to the textual analysis of abstracts of each element in my library. The textual analysis of abstracts

¹ NVivo is a qualitative data analysis (QDA) computer software package produced by QSR International. It allows researchers to organize, analyze and find insights in unstructured.

Article	123
Management	117

Source: Author's processing.

The first 5 words (Tab.2), namely "governance", "public", "good", "development" and "economic" are the most cited in all the summaries treated, which gives them the character of an important element for filtering the reference documents in the selection process.

As a matter of fact, this study draws upon an analysis of the literature from the perspective of an extended systematic literature review. Relevant studies were searched for in seven various sources: Scopus, Web of Science, Science Direct, Springer, ProQuest, Jstor and Google Scholar (Tab.3).

Table 3: The references collected by source

Sources	References in %
Scopus	42,61%
Web of Science	27,83%
Science Direct	21,30%
Jstor	3,04%
Springer	3,47%
ProQuest	1,30%
Google Scholar	0,43%

Source: Author's processing.

Some references were collected directly from editors of scientific journals, and others through databases and scientific search motors. Almost half (42.61%) of the studies originated from the Scopus source, followed by Web of Science and Science Direct, mainly due to their indexing of many journals that publish work on good public governance. Springer was especially the source for books and book chapters in this field, and ProQuest for the thesis. On Jstor only 3.04% of the documents have been downloaded because the subscription of the institution is thematic, delineating different transdisciplinary approaches, i.e. documents in management or economics. Indeed, Google Scholar has allowed me to find two articles of which only the abstract was available on the other sources.

The library of scientific articles is very rich and even diversified, it includes all the work published from the 1990s until 2020, and represents a portal towards 30 years of research in the field of public governance (Fig.2).

Figure 2: The references collected by year of publication

Source: Author's processing.

This justifies the fact that this topic is long-standing but still topical and inspires many authors to contribute to the development of knowledge in this area.

Nevertheless, it is important to read the most recent work to know the latest conclusions of the work that has been produced by the authors. This is why the papers of the last two years (Current year and 2019s, 2018s) are the most voluminous (Fig.2), it enables us to visualize and update the development of knowledge in this field.

In addition, and as notified above (Tab.1) 226 of the references are journal articles, so the questions that arises is, where are these articles published? Are there journals dedicated simultaneously on the same line of research? Effectively, the articles collected were published mainly in the journal "Governance", followed by "World Development", "Public Policy and Administration" and other journals presented in the graph below² (Fig.3)

Figure 3 : Main journals of corresponding papers

Source: Author's processing.

So, 32 selected articles were published in the journal of "Governance", 12 articles in "World Development" 12 in "Public Policy and Administration". Other papers were also recognized by the selection including 8 articles in each of "Land Use Policy" and "Public Management Review". And many other journals in which I have found important articles on the subject, listed with details of the number of articles for each one (Appendix 1).

² Only the journals with at least 2 articles were mentioned in the result.

2.2 Extended systemic literature review

From the established word cloud, I was able to identify where exactly each keyword appears, in which reference, and how many times. Even more, I was also able to identify where 4 or 5 or all the principal keywords appear together. Through this method I decided my references to be carefully read.

From the exploratory systemic literature review, I was able to select the most important references from different scientific databases, saved in my Zotero Library.

The academic literature on governance, good governance and sustainable development governance has grown rapidly. However, apart from the universal acceptance of its importance, differences prevail in respect of theoretical formulations, policy prescriptions and conceptualization of the subject itself and no one can claim ownership of the Governance however modern theories have expanded the connotation, focusing on a large variety of instruments designed to alter and channel the behavior of individual and collective actors (Loorbach, 2007; Pierre and Peters, 2000; Adger and Jordan, 2009; Kardos, 2012).

According to The World Bank governance work of Kaufmann, Kraay and Mastruzzi (2006) operates a set of aggregate governance indicators based on: access to voice and accountability; lack of political instability and violence; minimum government effectiveness; existing regulatory burden, the rule of law, concrete and visible efforts to eliminate bribery and corruption. (Daniel Kaufmann et al., 2009).

3. Findings and Discussion

Through the textual analysis of the full texts, a condensed template was developed through which the synthesis table was produced. The systematic literature review involves analyzing the selected documents in which the most frequent words in the abstracts appear. Either together or a minimum of 3 key words listed in (Tab.2).

The literature review allows us to situate our subject in relation with economic development.

Table 4 : Synthetic table of bibliographical references

Author /Year /Journal	Country	Problematic	Method	Main Findings
A.Goldsmith, A (2007) <i>Governance</i>	United Kingdom	How can developing countries boost their economic growth rates by introducing "good governance" measures? This paper examines this issue from the perspective of international development agencies.	An extensive analysis of specific governance reforms and its economic turnarounds Country case studies: United States, Argentina, Mauritius and Jamaica.	-The independence of meritocratic bureaucracies and judicial systems and the transparency of elections are worthy goals in themselves. This does not necessarily have to give a noticeable boost to development. -Good governance reforms are more effective than the cause of accelerated development per se, but over time they will be an important factor in sustaining development.

<p>Ardielli,E (2019) <i>Review of Economic Perspectives</i></p>	<p>Czech Republic</p>	<p>The evaluation of Good Governance development in the European Union countries in the long-term.</p>	<p>Application the method Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS). The original data used in the research were the values of Worldwide Governance Indicators monitored and processed by the World Bank. (In the period 2007–2017)</p>	<p>-The countries that have been successful in this area in the long-term, in particular, are the Nordic countries: Finland, Sweden and Denmark. -On the contrary, there are countries that show greater shortcomings in terms of Good Governance as Romania, Bulgaria and Greece.</p>
<p>Adams,S, Mengistu,B (2009) <i>Journal of Developing Societies</i></p>	<p>United Kingdom</p>	<p>The study examined the impact of privatization on economic growth and income inequality.</p>	<p>Application of the Least Squares Dummy Variable (LSDV) approach. In 82 developing countries between 1991 and 2002.</p>	<p>- The privatization did not have a significant impact on both income inequality and economic growth. - Good governance had a positive impact on economic growth and a negative impact on income inequality. - Foreign direct investment (FDI) had a positive effect on income inequality, but a negligible impact on economic growth.</p>
<p>AlBassam, Bassam A (2013) <i>European Journal of Sustainable Development</i></p>	<p>Saudi Arabia</p>	<p>The article studied whether the strong relationship between governance and growth exists during economic crises or only during non-crisis periods.</p>	<p>- The application of Correlations was conducted between GDP and each indicator of the six governance indicators for all countries using data from 2006 to 2011.</p>	<p>- The literature review demonstrated successfully the existence of the causal relationship between governance and economic growth, but not much is reported on the influence of the economic crisis on this connection. - A country's level of development influences the effect of the economic crisis on the governance-growth relationship. - As a result, countries at different levels of development have different requirements, they must improve governance and strengthen economic growth in times of crisis.</p>

<p>Kaufmann, D (2005) <i>Finance & Development</i></p>	<p>USA</p>	<p>Identification of the different "myths" that prevail over governance and corruption.</p>	<p>-Analyzing the data that suggest that transparency helps improve governance and reduce corruption, essential ingredients for better development and economic growth.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public disclosure is an indispensable part of transparency, which is a key to good governance (Disclosure of assets and income of candidates for public office, civil servants, politicians and legislators, judges and their dependents, individual and corporate contributions to political campaigns, campaign expenses, parliamentary votes, bills and parliamentary debates, budgets and public meetings.) - Effective implementation of conflict of interest laws, separating business, politics, legislation and public service, and adoption of a law governing lobbying, and the punishment of institutions found guilty of corruption in public procurements. - The right of access to information and freedom of all types of media is also a myth that prevail over governance and corruption. - Ensuring the diagnosis of governance and the anti-corruption process in order to implement transparency programs at the local level.
<p>Kaufmann, D. and Kraay,A. (2008) <i>Munich Personal RePEc Archive</i></p>	<p>USA</p>	<p>Distinction between The Worldwide Governance Indicators. Those that measure formal rules and those that measure the practical application of those rules. What are the strengths and weaknesses of the two types of indicators and the complementarities between them?</p>	<p>Method of measurement error in the assessments of the organizations, and of The Worldwide Governance Indicators</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - All the governance indicators contain a measurement error. But each indicator can reduce the influence of measurement error individually, by combining, organizing and summarizing information from different sources. - The Worldwide Governance Indicators (WGI) are aggregated indicators from a variety of sources, which combine information from a wide range of sources.
<p>Al Mamun, M et al. (2017) <i>Economic Modelling</i></p>	<p>Australia</p>	<p>Exploring the link between economic growth and resources.</p>	<p>The natural logarithm of GDP per capita (LGDPC) is used as a measure of</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - In countries with higher economic globalization, QOG has a positive and significant effect on economic growth.

		Does resource abundance facilitate or impede economic growth?	economic growth. The main independent variables are the natural logarithm of oil rent per capita (NORENT) and the governance quality index (GQI).	- Currently the ICTDIF is an emerging catalyst that influence significantly the status of essential goods and services and economic decision-making regarding the link between essential goods and services and economic growth.
Anttiroiko, A-V. (2017) <i>International Journal of Public Policy</i>	Finland	This article examined the preconditions for developing countries to benefit from the experiences of the world's least corrupt nations and their development paths. How to establish strong anti-corruption policy models that consider culture, democracy, political leadership and administrative apparatus?	the method employed is benchmarking between three success stories of good governance, those in Finland, New Zealand and Singapore, and their ability to serve as reference or models for developing countries seeking to eradicate corruption.	- Finland and New Zealand are countries with essentially evolutionary anti-corruption development path. - Successful Western countries have important similarities concerning the role of democracy, local culture, political leadership and administrative machinery in anti-corruption policy, which are embedded in their evolutionary development paths. Singapore is among top performers in Asia because it puts special emphasis on its political leadership and anti-corruption agency in eradicating corruption.
Al-Marhubi, F (2004) <i>Contemporary Economic Policy</i>	Sultanate Of Oman	Drawing on insights from economic, political, and cultural theories of governance, this article investigates the determinants of governance.	The method consists of testing the following hypothesis: the richest countries should enjoy better governance, using the logarithm of real Gross Domestic Product (GDP) per capita in 1960 as an overall measure of economic development. This analysis is based on cross-national data from 86 countries.	- Highly significant exogenous and historically predetermined variables: countries with a history of Western European influence and with origins in British common law have better governance. - Economic factors have a significant impact on governance: such as openness to trade, level of economic development and resource intensity of exports.

<p>Behera, A (2019) <i>Studies in Indian Politics</i></p>	<p>India</p>	<p>This article highlights the contradictions between the governance mechanisms and development measures towards the constitutional provisions related to the autonomy of local communities in the scheduled areas (SA) of central and eastern India.</p>	<p>The article interrogates the politics of control and management of natural resources through governance mechanisms and development initiatives. And identifies the commonalities between the state and the Maoists in terms of their control over the local communities.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The development and good governance initiatives of the state in the scheduled areas in India have only contributed to further deprivation and alienation of the local communities. -The issue of the territories affected by Maoist violence must be managed through a system of governance that crushes the systematic deprivation of natural resources. - The development and good governance initiatives must be based on the local needs rather than what is being decided from outside. - The article affirms that the state-led initiatives and the Maoist movement are both instruments in sustaining the conflict and alienation of the local communities.
<p>Noja, G-G. (2019) <i>International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health</i></p>	<p>Romania</p>	<p>This paper studied several fundamental credentials of good governance and public administration in relation with economic development, but also poverty, research, and development support, as representative socio-economic credentials in the European Union (EU) countries.</p>	<p>The empirical analysis is based on data covering the 1995–2017 lapse of time, processed through three econometric procedures, namely robust regression, structural equation modeling, and Gaussian graphical models.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The implications of public administration have an important impact on the socio-economic dimensions. - Public administration expenditure (especially support for the environment), has positive and significant implications for the EU economies, leading to a significant increase in per capita GDP and a reduction in the risk of poverty. - The quality of governance in EU countries requires an additional effort to build on good public governance to support long-term economic development.
<p>Grindle, M-S (2004) <i>Governance</i></p>	<p>USA</p>	<p>How to classify the different reforms to achieve good governance? This article has mainly addressed the issue of prioritizing good governance reforms to promote economic</p>	<p>The method carried out is the analysis of the good governance agenda which is based on the points mentioned in the World Development Reports: Characteristics of good governance,</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Interdependent links between the nature of policies and institutional arrangements and growth or poverty reduction. - Corruption and instability hamper development. Therefore, anti-corruption has to be prioritized as a reform towards good governance. - The structural disappearance of the adjustment policies promoted by the International

		development and reduce poverty.	Institutions for good governance, Specific laws, Specific policies, Specific services, General strategies to achieve, Specific objectives.	Monetary Fund and the World Bank in the 1980s and 1990s has contributed to the recognition that good governance is a key strategy for reducing poverty. - It is important to set priorities according to factors based on the characteristics of the country and public administrations, hierarchies of reform activities, effectiveness and capacity for policy impact, while distinguishing between short- and long-term objectives.
Hadj, S. et al. (2018) <i>International Economics</i>	Tunisia	Analysis of the relationship between governance and economic growth, focusing on the role of the exchange rate regime. Theoretically, good governance stimulates economic growth, but recently, some countries with weak governance are experiencing significant economic growth.	To resolve the problematic, the authors carried out GMM regressions on panel data to overcome problems of heteroskedasticity, autocorrelation and homogeneity. The panel covers the period 1996-2012 and includes 50 countries (21 developed and 29 emerging countries).	- Exchange rate flexibility is important for explaining the economic growth, it significantly destabilizes emerging markets, and accelerates economic growth in developed countries. - In emerging countries, exchange rate flexibility requires good governance, which in turn encourages the choice of a more flexible regime, with the aim of stimulating economic growth. - For developed countries, good governance accelerates economic growth if the exchange rate regime is not too flexible and exchange rate flexibility enhances economic activity if governance is not of good quality.
Epstein, G-S. Gang, I-N. (2019) <i>International Tax and Public Finance</i>	Germany	Since the payment of taxes owed differs between rich and poor, this paper explains how tax evasion and inequality can limit the capacity for economic development.	The methods used in this work : Relative efforts, winning probabilities, and the proposed enforcement level.	- People are engaged in a relative way in a struggle to determine the degree to which the tax is applied, whether they are rich or poor. - An efficient and transparent tax administration policy is an obligation to achieving good governance. But it must definitely be adequate to the requirements of society. - In order to achieve the highest global level of good governance, the Tax Administrator (TA) must make clear choices in the search for the mechanism over the whole range of tax administration instruments.

<p>Mgonja, B. E. S. (2010) <i>University of Alberta</i></p>	<p>Canada</p>	<p>Why do some countries and their systems of governance fail while others succeed? What is wrong with development initiatives in Africa? This manuscript concern the case of Tanzania</p>	<p>The approach is to establish a new institutional approach to research and analysis of the fundamental institutional issues of the contemporary system of public governance in Tanzania. To study the relationship between public institutions and governance in local political contexts in order to analyze the impacts of institutional factors on good governance.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public institutions of governance significantly influence the good governance and poverty reduction situation in Tanzania, which in turn influences development outcomes. - The functions of the institutions considered important for the achievement of good governance development objectives have become much simpler in Tanzania. - A dysfunction in the institutional mechanisms has a straightforward impact on the system of public governance. This is another perspective on good governance.
<p>Kardos, M (2012) <i>Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences</i></p>	<p>Romania</p>	<p>The Reflection of Good Governance in Sustainable Development Strategies</p>	<p>-Using as methodology the thematic content analysis, on how good governance is reflected in EU countries sustainable development strategies</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sustainable Development Strategies necessitate concern for and involvement of the various vertical coordination mechanisms. - Vertical coordination consists of disseminating good practices of the public consultation process in order to bring development strategies closer to the people. - These strategies can be portrayed as a change in their behavior to one that is increasingly sustainable.
<p>Kwasi Fosu, A (2017) <i>Rethinking Governance and Development</i></p>	<p>USA</p>	<p>The chapter provided an account of the role of governance in Africa's economic development.</p>	<p>Overview of the findings that show that Africa as a region, since about the end of the 1990s, has significantly improved per capita income, the level of human development and reduced poverty.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -The results revealed that economic governance is measured by economic freedom, political governance is measured by the Electoral Competitiveness Index, and executive constraint is measured by political stability indicators. - Negative implications for the allocation of fiscal resources lead to a likely disequilibrium between the economy and politics.

<p>Liu, J et al. (2018) <i>Economies</i></p>	<p>China</p>	<p>This paper investigated the impact of governance quality on economic growth in China.</p>	<p>This article reviewed the panel data in the provincial regions in China over the period 2001-2015. Methodology: Build a new comprehensive index of provincial governance, with verification of the robustness of the empirical results.</p>	<p>-Improving the quality of local governance is necessary, as well as promoting human capital accumulation to simulate the sustainable development of the Chinese economy. - The quality of governance has a positive effect on economic growth, because good governance significantly strengthens the "outstretched hand" or significantly weakens the "outstretched hand" of power. - In the Eastern region, better governance brings good quality economic development, contrary to the Western region where better governance brings rapid economic growth but no development.</p>
<p>Omri, A. Ben Mabrouk, N. (2020) <i>Environmental Impact Assessment Review</i></p>	<p>Saudi Arabia, And Tunisia</p>	<p>The effectiveness of good governance in rebalancing the economic, environmental, and social components of sustainable development.</p>	<p>Good economic, political, and institutional governance are considered as conditional variables, which allow rebalancing these three components in the case of 20 selected MENA economies for the period 1996–2014. Using simultaneous-equation modeling approach.</p>	<p>- Political and institutional governance contributes positively to sustainable development, there are reciprocal links between human development and economic growth, which means that they are interlinked and can very well complement each other. - The paper enhances that political and institutional governance enables MENA governments to moderate the negative impacts of carbon emissions on economic growth and human development and also the positive impact of economic growth on emissions growth, and hence on sustainable development.</p>
<p>Bauer, M-W. Becker, S (2014) <i>Journal of European Integration</i></p>	<p>Germany</p>	<p>The governance architecture has undergone changes in the European Union (EU), particularly with regard to the function of the European Commission regarding the institutional</p>	<p>An empirical study of Overview of changes in Commission's role in economic governance. four areas that have undergone the most important changes: support for financial stability,</p>	<p>-The Commission continues to play a leading role in the economic governance of the EU, but it is constantly changing. - Its authority to set the agenda is diminishing, as most economic governance decisions depend on the Commission to make them work. This finding qualifies the degree of intergovernmentalism in economic governance.</p>

		reforms and their consequences.	economic policy surveillance, coordination of national policies and supervision of the financial sector.	
Huang, C-J Ho, Y-H (2017) <i>The North American Journal of Economics and Finance</i>	Taiwan	The impact of good governance on economic growth in Asia.	In order to determine a Granger causality ranging from governance to economic growth, this paper used a frequency-domain approach existing in twelve Asian countries, classified as "free", "partly free" and "non-free", over the period 1996-2014.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Empirical results highlight that "free" countries show no significant causality ranging from most dimensions of governance to economic growth, except the case of South Korea. Concerning the "partially free" countries, with the exception of Indonesia and Thailand, Granger rule of law is at the origin of economic growth. - Regarding "non-free" countries, a significant causality is inferred, ranging from most dimensions of governance, particularly for government effectiveness and the rule of law, to economic growth. - Particular attention should be accorded to effective government and the rule of law for "non "free" countries. This implies growth in Real per capita GDP.

Source : *Author's processing.*

The processes of good governance must include participation by the important stake holders in the decision making. The processes need to emphasize decentralization of power structure and participation in decision making (Kaufmann et al., 2004).

The study of good governance can be focused of the broad-based stake- holders and using its financial, natural, and human resources in the interests of all people, and on the basis of the principles of justice, fairness, equity, efficiency, transparency, and accountability (Farazmand, 2020). Also, one of the major elements of good governance is decentralization of administration. “Decentralization can contribute to improved performance of local government; it can provide new opportunities for responsiveness to local needs; it can mean that if governance improves citizens may hold public officials and agencies more accountable. Decentralization is not a linear or consistent process, and it can suffer reverses as often as advances in terms of how local governments and citizens take up its challenges”(Grindle, 2007). Another way adopted by Mgonja, B. E. S.(2010) , to analyze good governance of public systems in Tanzania is the functioning of institutional mechanisms. this study revealed the importance

of public institutions, and their role considered necessary for the achievement of development goals.

However, governance research developed into a more mature paradigm based on conceptual clarity, a broad range of shared theories and methods, and empirical investigation both of the scope conditions and the societal impacts of governance processes based on multi-actor collaboration (Ansell & Torfing, 2016; Sørensen & Torfing, 2018)

Good governance is operationally defined by the various indicators on available data based on the UN statistics. For this research, good (bad) governance is measured by an index based on available data. The index includes: Lower Political Rights, Lower Civil Liberties, Corruption Perception Index, Satisfaction with Life Index, Global Gender Gap Index, Lower Political Risk Index, Human Development Index, Gini Index, Lower Education Attainment Level (Jamil et al., 2013). It also combines hands-off tools such as institutional design and political, juridical and discursive framing with hands-on tools such as process management, direct participation and conversation (Bell & Hindmoor, 2009)

The first generations of governance research not only helped to clarify the concept of governance (Kooiman, 2003) but also provided a thorough understanding of how interactive forms of governance contribute to advancing the effectiveness and democratic quality of modern governance (Sørensen & Torfing, 2018). Concerning Al Mamun et al. (2017) who considered that the linkage between resources and economic growth is an unresolved empirical puzzle with major opposing strands toward the quality of governance.

In this frame of literature review, it is debatable whether how good governance practices lead to economic growth or to economic development. Among the works that focused on this issue of public governance in economic development Kaufmann et al. (2004) claimed that governance quality and economic growth are positively related. In their evaluation of the worldwide governance indicators (WGI) from 1996 to 2002, they found that “per capita incomes and the quality of governance are strongly positively correlated across countries”

On the one hand, there is a multitude of works (Anttiroiko, 2017; Epstein & Gang, 2019; Goldsmith, 2007; Grindle, 2007; Daniel Kaufmann, 2005) that have opted for corruption and the effort made by the State to control and reduce corruption as an explicative variable to conduct the study in terms of good governance, to subsequently generate it on the economic aspect.

In the other hand a very important question is about the interdependence of Good Governance and socio-economic development (Haldenwang, 2004 and Agere, 2000). Governance improvement and country development are considered to be related issues. Many authors discuss the relationship of the implementation of governance reforms and rapid economic and social development. (Ardielli, 2019).

Noja et al. (2019) concluded that an overview of the implications of public administration for the economy and development is significant in analyzing the relationship between good public governance and sustainable economic development. As AlBassam (2013) argued, some explanatory variables could contribute more than others to the analysis of the impact of good governance on economic growth. For example, a country's type of political system could influence how the economic crisis shapes the relationship between governance and growth in that country. Kwon & Kim (2014) determined a causal link between good governance and poverty reduction, out of the six WGIs tested, and the empirical evidence does not support the hypothesis that good governance leads to poverty reduction. In contrast to Grindle, (2004) that shows that the good governance has become a paramount strategy for reducing poverty, following the structural disappearance of the adjustment policies, promoted by the IMF and the World Bank in the 1980s and 1990s.

As for Kwasi Fosu (2014), he developed economic governance philosophy as a result of its intersecting research between good governance and economics in his book of *Rethinking Governance and Development*, he concluded that the economic governance measured by economic freedom and political governance by the index of electoral competitiveness, and executive constraint and by indicators of political stability (2017). In Addition, Bauer & Becker (2014) analyzed the economic governance, they focused on supranational executive's role in the four areas of European Commission that have witnessed the most important changes: financial stability support, economic policy surveillance, coordination of national polices and supervision of the financial sector.

By that reasoning, to measure economic growth, GDP is generally employed, and to study the impact of good governance, one or more aggregate governance indicators are used. Nevertheless, the results of this study indicate that policymakers in countries should choose to pay more attention to the quality of governance, particularly with regard to government effectiveness and the rule of law, in order to promote the future growth rate of real GDP per capita (Huang & Ho, 2017).

The relationship between the quality of governance and the economy demonstrates that governance quality has a positive effect on economic development (Anttiroiko, 2017; Liu et al., 2018) i.e. that good governance presents diminishing marginal returns, which means that the high-speed economic growth effect becomes less and less, . i.e. while the high-quality economic development effect becomes more and more, At least in the developed countries, such are the cases studied in China, New Zealand, Finland and Singapore.

Likewise, Adams & Mengistu (2008) found that good governance had a positive impact on economic growth and a negative impact on income inequality in their work in 82 developing countries. Omri & Ben Mabrouk (2020) were concerned with economic development, but in its sustainable aspect. But they also deduced that political and institutional governance - which are part of good public governance - contribute positively to the components of sustainable development. Through this research, we understand that there are reciprocal links between human development and economic growth, and that one impacts the other.

It turns out that during economic crises, most governments focus more on economic growth than on governance development (Daniel Kaufmann et al., 2009). It must also be affirmed that in order to successfully carry out public strategies in terms of governance, development and good governance initiatives must first be based on the local needs of the country.

According to the requirements of its population and economy rather than on what is decided from outside, for example, on the case of the study in India (Behera, 2019).

Altogether, several academic research studies have examined the relationship between good public governance and the economy of a country, which can be classified according to the impact on economic growth, economic development, or the economic regulatory and legal framework.

Furthermore, this theoretical paper studied the contribution of governance on economic development. It is part of the normative theory of the public economy which is interested in market failure. The economic development emphasizes the importance of the distributive and corrective role of the state in dealing with the imperfections and externalities engendered by irresponsible behavior fueled by the feeling of not being afraid of penalties.(Hadj Fraj et al., 2018)

4. Conclusion

The research study was selected according to a two-step procedure. First, the search results were filtered by title and then by abstract (Exploratory Systematic Literature Review), and then

reduced according to strict inclusion and exclusion criteria. Those excluded were references to studies that were a title and an abstract far from the subject matter. The other studies were selected for a full text search (Extended Systematic Literature Review) They were thoroughly read and understood.

This paper has revealed through an extended systemic literature review that good governance is a prerequisite for economic development, by cross-referencing the ideas of different authors, multitudes of works, and even incompatible results. This is because of the territory and time in which the studies were conducted.

Each country has its specific characteristics, its political history, and its own public management process. In the final part of the document, the study examined that Good governance in public area is pivotal to contemporary national of economic development strategy, it contributes to long-term strategic policy objectives and involvement, to the coherence of policies through vertical and horizontal coordination.

Consequently, good governance is an open and transparent process that carries out the involvement, integration and accountability of stakeholders and brings economic development strategies closer together. The results of the study suggest that particular country characteristics may be more important in promoting growth than any economic policy in itself. This and other important issues may be subject for future research.

Finally, in the hope that this work will open the search for more productive research in the intersection of the disciplines of public management and economics, which is a potentially fruitful area of scientific research.

Appendices

Appendix 1: List of principal journals

Principal journals	Number of corresponding sources
Governance	32
World Development	12
Public Policy and Administration	12
Land Use Policy	8
Public Management Review	8
The Journal of Politics	6
The European Journal of Development Research	6
International Journal of Project Management	4
Safety Science	4
International Journal of Public Administration	4
Economic Modelling	4
Journal of Comparative Economics	4
Technological Forecasting and Social Change	4
Annual Review of Political Science	4
Journal of Environmental Management	4
International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction	2
Procedia technology	2
The Social Science Journal	2
The Journal of Strategic Information Systems	2
European Journal of Law and Economics	2
Asian Journal of Business Ethics	2
Group Decision and Negotiation	2
European Union Politics	2
Biopolymers	2

International Journal of Public Sector Management	2
Organization Studies	2
Academy of Management Journal	2
Energy Exploration & Exploitation	2
International Economics	2
The North American Journal of Economics and Finance	2
Journal of Developing Societies	2
Comparative Economic Studies	2
Journal of Economic Issues	2
Economies	2
African Development Review	2
Studies In Comparative International Development	2
Journal of Business Ethics	2
Kyklos	2
The British Accounting Review	2
Urban Forum	2
Knowledge and Policy	2
Evaluation and Program Planning	2
Development and Change	2
Journal of Accounting Literature	2
Global Environmental Change	2
Hague Journal on the Rule of Law	2
The World Bank Research Observer	2
The World Bank Economic Review	2
Finance and Development	2

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